

POLICY BRIEF

InterAgency Institute
BEYOND INSTITUTIONAL BOUNDARIES

A “SIDE EFFECT”: VACCINE HESITANCY

Authors:

Juliana Miranda Martins

i

Thais Mantovani Balac

ii

POLICY STATEMENT

The pandemic brought with it a change in social behavior that ranges from restrictions on individual freedom, the expansion of social exclusion and poverty, changes in the labor market, the forced implementation of distance learning, inadequacy in the public transport system and problems from logistics, to the return of inflation and a series of “new rules” that produce countless social and psychological effects in post-modern societies. Among so many forced and/or necessary changes, we will discuss in this policy brief a “side effect” that emerges within the Covid-19 pandemic: the phenomenon of vaccine hesitancy. Such apparently harmless behavior implies irreparable loss of life considering the speed of mutation of the virus and the spread of the disease. Although the COVID-19 pandemic has been one of the greatest challenges faced by humanity since the second world war and the development of vaccines to combat SARS-COV-2 has represented an extraordinary advance for the international scientific community and saved millions of lives around the world, there is a portion of the population that delays the decision to receive the immunizing agent. The success of the vaccination campaign will depend on when hesitantly they are vaccinated and, in the course of the fourth wave, on the speed of decision-making of these individuals.

BACKGROUND

Together with the development of the first vaccine – in 1796 against smallpox – came also criticism, low confidence and hesitancy against it. So it is not something new or a surprise to find lots of resistance against covid-19 vaccines. Historically, even facing challenging situations to convince the population about the efficacy of the vaccines the outcomes were very good: vaccine does work, it saves life and is possible to eradicate diseases with vaccination.

“Vaccination hesitation” is defined as the behavior of individual resistance and of private reach, in which the individual is reluctant to be inactivated due to their own doubts about the effectiveness and safety of the vaccine, resulting in a personal and, consequently, social delay of the campaign of vaccination. This brief instrumental definition serves to differentiate it from other types of ideological positioning

against immunizing agents, which, although they are closely interconnected, will not be dealt with in this text: “denialism” (in which the false conviction that the virus does not exist) and the NO VAXs movements. This last group is defined by an individual who, in the social or virtual environment, does not vaccinate and/or mobilizes third parties against immunizing agents. The shadows of this position continue with those individuals who reject any type of vaccine, those who reject only the vaccine against Covid-19 (or from a particular pharmaceutical company), those who are vaccinated or not, are against the mandatory vaccination or against to the vaccine passport. The issue is complex and is still evolving.

In an extreme unequal world, the percentage of vaccination in a county is directly related to the county's economic wealth where rich countries have a bigger and more reachable vaccination programmes than poor countries. Groups against vaccination are also more present in richer countries, usually questioning the safety of vaccines and pointing that some vaccines are related to increase of autism cases or other diseases.

When the first vaccines against COVID-19 were developed, a kind of “global race to acquire vaccines” began, strongly determined by the wealth of the country organized according to the laws of the market. The ones who invested more in research and development got the first deals, letting developed countries still in precarious situation related to access of doses. While Israel is considering giving a fourth round of doses to its population, Haiti, Chad, Burundi and Congo did not even get 1% of their population vaccinated. While some countries have not yet enough doses, others are in another situation, like the case of South Africa, they asked Johnson & Johnson and Pfizer to defer vaccine deliveries because the vaccination uptake was below expected (just around 35 percent of South African adults are fully vaccinated) and supply was not anymore an issue. Romania was also in a similar situation: a low percentage of the population engaged in vaccination leaving the country with a big supply and a decision to sell a significant amount of doses to Ireland. Portugal, Malta, Iceland and Ireland are the European countries with the highest percentage of fully vaccinated people, while Bulgaria and Romania have the lowest rates, just 22 percent are fully vaccinated. The vaccine hesitancy can be found in lots of countries and in each one different aspects needs to be considered to fully understand this groups and why they are hesitant towards covid-19 vaccination.

There are also the critics related to how vaccines are made, and some substances can be harmful, as is the case of the use of mercury (thimerosal) as a preservative in vaccines. This was strongly criticized and lead to innumerous research studies to assess the safety of vaccines. None of them has found a link between vaccines and autism and related to the mercury substance. Although there is no clear scientific evidence that small amounts of thimerosal in vaccines cause harm, in July 1999, a leading U.S. public health and medical organizations and vaccine manufacturers agreed that thimerosal should be reduced or eliminated from vaccines as a precautionary measure. As much as there are arguments against vaccination, accordingly to Our World in Data, overall the widespread public concern for vaccine safety does not appear to be strongly correlated with vaccination rates, and one of the best examples is France, where while one-third of the French public disagrees with their safety, 97% of children are vaccinated [1].

RESULTS

To use as a way of comparison, smallpox, a serious and very infectious disease, was eradicated thanks to the efficient use of vaccines, but this did not come without conflict, protests and hesitancy. Back then, doctors gained notoriety and personal fame claiming to be the only one's brave enough to point against the risks of vaccination, usually arguing that the vaccines were more dangerous than the disease. Historian Michael Bliss in his non-fiction account, **Plague: A Story of Smallpox in Montreal**, bring us to a very similar situation we are witnessing right now with Covid-19 pandemic. In Montreal, Canada, in 1885 the arguments against vaccination were very similar as the ones we are familiar now and can be summarized in few points: vaccines are more dangerous than the disease; vaccines cause a range of other diseases; media and governments are inflating the number of cases and deaths to alarm and create panic in the population; mandatory vaccinations are outrageous on personal liberty.

In Ireland a strong voice against vaccination is Ms Dolores Cahill, a former professor at University College Dublin. Ms Cahill was previously a highly respected academic in the field of proteomics, which is the large-scale study of proteins and spend years in the prestigious Max Planck Institute in Germany before returning to Ireland where she had taught a UCD first-year medicine class, called Science, Medicine and Society. Ms Cahill started to gain notoriety during the pandemic taking parts in rallies across Europe criticizing lockdown measures, the use of masks and also minimizing other covid-19 risks. She got court charges in the UK for one of this rallies that were taken during lockdown when the congregation of bigger groups were not allowed.

She founded a Covid-19 network – World Doctors Alliance – whose members are academics and doctors. The WDA is just one of a number of groups founded by Ms Cahill to spread misinformation on the virus both in Ireland and abroad. The group Facebook page has been removed recently due to misinformation about covid-19. In the midst of extensive amount of fake news and misinformation but with strong support even coming from the medical community the levels of doubt and fear in the society can be very high. According to a recent report by the International Monetary Fund [2], a number of people are still reluctant to get vaccinated, this number ranges from around 10-20% of people in the UK to around 50% in Japan and 60% in France.

All these aspects are important to identify where and why some groups are more hesitant than others to accept the vaccines, and a more culturally tailored message will have higher chances in addressing this challenge.

Writing in the Journal of the Royal Society of Medicine, a group of population health, demographic, epidemiology and behavioural scientists propose an approach focused on the **5Cs: confidence, complacency, convenience, communication and context**, - to tackle vaccines hesitancy.

Another point that should be strongly considered is a more widespread feeling that pharmaceutical companies cannot be trusted. The pharmaceutical industry, between 1991 and 2012, is responsible for paying \$35.7 billion for numerous violations just in the United States and these scandals just pave the way to a lack of trust in such companies. Just before the covid-19 pandemic, a report published in September 2019, found that pharma had the worst reputation of all industries according to the American public [4]. The public criticism is mainly related to high drug costs and a perception that these companies will favour profits on behalf of people's lives with their predatory business practices. The fact that this industry has been engaging in bad behaviour for several decades have now turned a percentage of the public against it. Vaccines are already proven to be very efficient in preventing serious diseases and death, and other medications are also getting approved to be used as covid-19 treatment, but more time will be necessary to see how these tools to fight the pandemic will impact big pharma reputation in the general public.

CONCLUSIONS

From the point of view of the collective perception of the COVID-19 Pandemic, two phases could be identified: the first triggers the contamination of countries and the establishment of the global pre-vaccine crisis. During this phase, the virus was considered a worldwide problem and despite the fact that countries had different economic resources, the emergency generated a sense of global solidarity. After the development of the vaccine, paradoxically, this solidarity in times of crisis was abruptly broken and a climate of competition for the vaccine prevailed. While the Pandemic has established itself as a common global problem, vaccination campaigns were developed by States in an individualized and competitive manner, that is, following the laws of the market and generating deep inequalities in obtaining immunizations.

This scenario of the "law of the strongest" generated mistrust in the capacity of institutions (especially in Europe where there are a large number of hesitant and NO VAX) to guarantee access to the immunizing agent. Many doubts, criticisms and fake news were addressed to the WHO about what would be its roll in relation to member countries, what competence it would have to regulate the distribution of the vaccine, etc.

During the G20 called "*Vertice Mondiale sulla Salute*", held in Rome (May 2021) [5] a debate was expected on the breach of patents for the vaccine against COVID-19, which unfortunately disappeared from the discussion agenda. Some countries, including the United States, had given a positive signal to unlink the patents, but Germany was against it, influencing Italy and France.

Another factor of vaccine hesitation in the Eurozone was the fragmentation of the protocols to combat the pandemic that even with the "Declaration of Rome" where the commitment to homogenization of anti-Covid measures was affirmed. Another theme was the implementation of the right of universal access to vaccination, which was established with a long delay and the effects are disastrous, especially for the African continent.

RECOMMENDATIONS

One of the characteristics of reflexive societies is the search for information on the web and the comparison with measures adopted in other countries. The limits of European consensus and the absence of a homogeneous European policy and protocols increased the feeling of social insecurity and the trivialization of social restriction measures, especially by NO VAX groups that used such information to base their arguments.

In Europe the debate refers to the mandatory vaccination, which is different from the compulsory vaccination. While a compulsory rule justifies the use of force against an individual, a mandatory just adds some cost to a certain decision. In case of mandatory vaccination, an individual who still decides not to get vaccinated he/she is not allowed to enter certain places, otherwise he/she gets a fine. Contrary to what the anti-vax movement makes people believe, the state will never force a vaccine in someone's arms in case of mandatory vaccination, which would be a violation of his/her body integrity and a breach of the the Nuremberg Code (1947) [6]. Moreover, mandatory vaccination is not an infringement of our basic rights. It is supported by the argument that our individual choice contributes to the common good and that we are collectively responsible for our choices.

Within public policies in the field of public health, the issue of mandatory vaccination has been shown to be a disaggregating factor and has raised levels of misunderstanding and distrust even among European vaccinees. The recommendation would be a capillary action of health agents in the territory to act on the front line to talk with the hesitant groups. Interviewing these individuals and listening to the reason for their hesitation can reveal what kind of information reaches these groups. In this sense, it is crucial to obtain a map that reveals geographic, cultural and social factors that influence hesitation: for example, communities of elders who have not participated in mass vaccination campaigns in the past, rural populations who think that their geographic location plays a role in their protection, etc.

We recommend an international cooperation to fight against fake news about the Pandemic and the vaccines, making groups and individuals responsible for publishing and replying to fake news. But also the big social media, like Facebook, Youtube and Instagram, should be on the front line and develop more efficient tools to report eventual false or misleading information to the authorities.

REFERENCES

- (1) <https://ourworldindata.org/vaccine-skepticism>
- (2) <https://www.imf.org/en/Publications/WP/Issues/2021/05/06/Who-Doesnt-Want-to-be-Vaccinated-Determinants-of-Vaccine-Hesitancy-During-COVID-19-50244>

- (3) COVID-19 vaccine hesitancy: the five Cs to tackle behavioural and socio-demographic factors (DOI: 10.1177/01410768211018951) by Mohammad S Razai, Pippa Oakeshott, Aneez Esmail, Charles Shey Wiysonge, Kasisomayajula Viswanath and Melinda C Mills will be published by the Journal of the Royal Society of Medicine at 00:05 hrs (UK time) on Thursday 3 June 2021.
- (4) <https://www.europeanpharmaceuticalreview.com/article/132222/has-covid-19-changed-public-perception-of-pharmaceutical-companies/>
- (5) GLOBAL HEALTH SUMMIT, Rome Declaration, European Union: https://global-health-summit.europa.eu/rome-declaration_en
- (6) <https://www.irishtimes.com/opinion/mandatory-vaccination-not-the-same-as-compulsory-1.4774909>

ⁱ Ph.D. in Economic Sciences of University of Alicante (Spain) and Ph.D. History and Cultural Anthropology of University of Padova (Italy).

ⁱⁱ Ph.D. in Political Scientist of IUPERJ (IESP) Rio de Janeiro (Brazil).